

STOCK PRICE ANALYSIS AND PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract— Stock price forecasting plays a vital role in influencing investors, organizations, and consumers in the securities market. Factors such as market volatility, Federal Reserve rate cuts, and CPI data significantly impact stock prices. This study offers a comprehensive overview of diverse prediction techniques such as sentiment analysis, machine learning, deep learning, and time series analysis, enhancing accuracy and reliability. Coupled with technical analysis, these techniques provide an effective method for implementing shareholder strategies from various perspectives. Deep learning models, known as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), contribute to precise predictions. Additionally, various machine learning models, including Decision Trees, Random Forest, AdaBoost, and XGBoost, augment the predictive framework. These methods emphasize the significance of feature engineering, model assessment, and technical analysis in explaining stock price strategies.

Keywords—Stock price prediction, Machine Learning, Deep learning, Technical analysis, LSTM networks, Feature engineering, Model evaluation

I. INTRODUCTION

The choice of approaches and algorithms has a significant effect on how well predictive models function in the financial domain. We all know that stock markets are having high volatility and volumes of data, it can be difficult to predict stock prices with any degree of accuracy. Old odd methods are unable to fully represent the complicated structure of stock market dynamics. These techniques often stop short in predicting nonlinear correlations between stock market movements and other parameters like investor emotion.

In the modern financial market environment, tips about stocks comes from various sources, including financial bulletin articles and social media platforms, in addition to historical stock price data. The necessity for more modernized prediction techniques that may produce excellent results has increased as a outcome of the integration of external variables. The theory suggests investigating cutting-edge methods that go against conventional statistical approaches. Our main area of interest is the techniques and algorithms that alter the landscape of stock price forecast accuracy by using the theoretical insights of sentiment analysis, crowd intelligence, and deep learning. Innovative methods are used in these fantastic strategies to extract, analyse, and learn from a variety of data sources. The Exploration of the Long Short Term Memory (LSTM)

neural network, a kind of recurrent neural network (RNN), stands out in particular as a powerful tool for capturing dependencies across lengthy sequences of data.

The calculated design and selection of input characteristics is mentioned as "Feature Engineering" & it helps the selected algorithms realise their latent predictive potential. The investors need to gain insights about how different techniques can enhance the accuracy of stock price prediction.

II. RESEARCH DATA

GUANGYU MU et al.[1], offers a revolutionary method called MS-SSA-LSTM that integrates sentiment analysis, swarm intelligence, and deep learning to predict Equity prices reliably. The proposed model extracts investor sentiment from financial news publications and internet sources data using a special sentiment dictionary. The hyperparameters of the LSTM model, which are performed using the extracted sentiment features and historical stock price data, are optimised using the Sparrow Search Algorithm. The experimental findings show that the proposed model exceeds existing deep learning models and conventional statistical techniques in terms of accuracy when making predictions.

Mojtaba Nabipour et al.[2] explains how to forecast stock market movements utilising machine learning techniques. The analysis examines past information spanning 10 years from four stock market segments, including diversified financials, petroleum, non-metallic minerals, and basic metals. Eleven prediction models, comprising nine Machine Learning Models and two Deep Learning algorithms, are presented and addressed by the authors. Overall, the research offers views into the efficiency of various methods for estimating stock market movements, which been observed in Tehran Stock Exchange investors.

Desheng Dash Wu et al.[3] focuses on the difficulties of predicting stock markets and suggests a cost-sensitive strategy to cope with these difficulties. The authors provide a unique labelling system that includes a threshold value to take market activity-related transaction costs into consideration. The study also looks at how cost-sensitive learning can be used to achieve returns at the lowest possible cost, which is sometimes more crucial for investors than maximising accuracy. The findings demonstrate that the

suggested cost sensitive strategy may successfully lower the price of international investments and increase profitability. At last, this study gives us knowledge on the usage of machine learning models for stock market forecasting and emphasises the need to take into account cost sensitive applications in this field.

Mahinda Mailagaha Kumbure et al.[4] highlighted that previous evaluations frequently focused on library analysis, finding highly cited publications and individuals, while giving few aspects about the estimation techniques, input factors, and data used in this research. The current work was motivated by the lack of knowledge to offer a thorough analysis of machine learning models that are usually used in financial forecasting. In-depth analyses of forecasting methodologies, the subtleties of input variables and data sources, and a close examination of particular variables and variable types utilised in the speaking of market forecasts are all covered in the study, that offers a better view than earlier evaluations.

Mohamed Sharaf et al.[5] tells that it is a habit for researchers to analyse earlier literature to expand on current knowledge and spot research gaps that influence their work. These connected studies may include conventional theories of portfolios and number of Machine Learning models for stock prediction, and also earlier attempts to optimise portfolios using various methods and techniques. Researchers can place their investigation within the larger framework of earlier research and highlight the originality and contributions of their suggested strategy by looking at and citing comparable work.

YOUNGBIN KIM et al.[6] assumes that predicting stock prices includes using a variety of data sources and algorithms. Researchers use text-based data from news and social media including numerical elements from previous market data. For time-series modelling, they frequently employ Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) such as LSTM and GRU, to identify sequential trends. Several models investigate the impact of business events on stock prices while others include sentiment analysis to identify investor feelings from text. Transformer encoders capture temporal correlations inside and between stocks, whereas graph-based systems describe inter-company interactions.

NAGARAJ NAIK et al.[7] describes correlations between the shares and currency rates, the usage of Support Vector Machines (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), specifically in a setting of Korean stock market information, and the application of Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models alone or in combination to capture non-linear patterns. The article also discusses the importance of Deep Neural Networks (DNN) which will validate the scant literature on equity crisis prediction, giving ideas for extended research in this field. The paper offers insightful analyses of the various price forecasting techniques and their applications.

Daiyou Xiao et al.[8] offers an overview of how Machine Learning Models are being used within the banking industry, particularly to forecast stock values using both conventional and machine learning models. The study depicts the case study of a New York Stock Exchange dataset that spans the years 2010 to 2019. To predict stock prices and their correlations among them the two basic models such as ARIMA (autoregressive integrated moving average) and LSTM (long short-term memory) neural networks are used. The outcome of experimentation shows that all of the models have the ability of accurately forecasting correlations and shares, with LSTM beating ARIMA in this regard.

Xianghui Yuan et al.[9] analyses the financial stability of several combined choices of stock models that contain various feature selection and stock price trend prediction algorithms. They construct such models using methods including feature selection, time-sliding windows for cross validation, and supervised methods. When choosing the top 1% of equities, the RF-RF integrated model occupies a place of profitable, producing a 29.51% annualised return. With an annualised return of 21.92% and a manageable maximum drawdown of 13.58% from 2011 to 2018, further examination utilising a divided back- testing approach supports the model's profitability.

Jui-sheng chou et al.[10] explains how to preview stock prices using support vector regression, also known as SVR, and its variation, least squares support vector regression. LSSVR is renowned for depending on hyperparameter adjustment for optimum performance and is praised for its effectiveness in addressing massive regression issues. Artificial bee colonies, cuckoo searches, particle swarm optimisation, and the firefly optimisation method are just a few examples of nature inspired optimisation methods that are being involved to automate the hyperparameter optimisation process. Particular values are placed on the firefly algorithm (FA) due to its effectiveness in resolving numerous optimisation issues, including market price predictions. Fundamentals and their variations are referred to be effective tools for design and engineering optimisation jobs.

Sharanya Banerjee et al.[11] discusses several techniques that are evaluated on technical analysis such as simple linear regression models, support vector machines with Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) with sentiment analysis, Hidden Markov Models, hybrid models using sentiment analysis and clustering methods, LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) networks, and LSTM combined with clustering methods. Each of these algorithms aims to anticipate stock prices.ck prices and trends.

KYUNGBOK MIN et al.[12] explains how to utilise stock fundamentals to anticipate stock price trends by analysing the correlation between financial news stories and historical price movements in stocks. Although earlier studies demonstrated the efficacy of such methods, they frequently ignored the structural links inside phrases. Due to its capacity to preserve memory across numerous time steps, recurrent neural networks are presented to be most effective alternative to convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for text and audio processing. However, when it comes to dependency over time, RNNs experience the issue of gradients disappearing. long short term memory and a model known as Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) units are suggested as remedies to this problem, with GRU being statistically more effective. Schuster's model is where the concept of a two-stream GRU was first introduced, and it is also introduced in the context which demonstrates how machine learning algorithms are utilised for predicting stock price trends by examining the relationship among financial news items and past stock price changes. Even if past research showed that these techniques worked, they typically overlooked the structural links inside phrases.

HAMED JABANI et al.[13]. gives information about how to properly estimate stock trends using a combination of algorithms and methodologies. Firstly, it utilises different economic indicators, including the Simple Moving Average (SMA), Weighted Moving Average (WMA), Momentum (MOM), Stochastic Oscillator (STCK), Stochastic Oscillator Signal Line (STCD), Larry Williams Percent Range (LWR),

Moving Average Convergence Divergence (MACD), Accumulation/Distribution Oscillator (ADO), Relative Strength Index (RSI), and Commodity Channel Index (CCI), to identify important characteristics from economic information. To avoid the dominance of higher values, these parameters are then normalised to a range of (0, +1). To depict higher (+1) or downwards (-1) stock movements, the article also presents the binary data technique, which transforms continuous value indicators into binary forms.

Jingyi Shen et al.[14] claims that the data feature selection had scrutinised, with Pira Muthu examining multiple approaches utilising diverse information to give insight into their effectiveness in improving decision tree performance. Hassan and Nath used Hidden Markov Models (HMM) to forecast the stock market, highlighting a straightforward method devoid of specialised expertise. As shown by Lee and Weng et al, respectively, commonly used SVM and Ensemble approaches shown the ability for recommendations in stock price prediction space. Meanwhile, McNally et al. and Sirignano Cont have used the development of deep learning, involving recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and long short term memory (LSTM) networks, by the challenging tokenization of Bitcoin and global financial sector prediction.

AUDELIANO WOLIAN LI et al.[15] presents a rigorous and structured method for locating, analysing, and discussing pertinent scholarly works to respond to particular research problems. This method is known as the systematic review process, and it is thoroughly described by Kitchenham and Charters. By following a rigorous process, the evaluation is kept objective and solid from a scientific standpoint. The main stages are communication, carrying out, and outcome analysis. Researchers develop the study objectives that will direct the systematic review during the planning stage. They also set specific inclusion, exclusion, and quality criteria for identifying pertinent articles. These inquiries guide the review's overall direction and define its scope and emphasis. Using definite search terms and techniques, reputable databases like Scopus, Web of Science (WoS), and IEEE Xplore are systematically mined for relevant papers throughout the analysis stage. To reduce the choice process, this step also involves eliminating duplicate content and using criteria for inclusion with the exclusion.

Nicolai petkov et al.[16] indicates that Henrique et al.'s (2019) bibliometric study offers a historical view, illustrating the frequent usage of methods like ARIMA, SVM, decision trees, and neural networks for forecasting different elements of the equity market. By categorising publications based on input factors, Bustos and Pomares- Quimbaya (2020) highlight current trends and emphasise the data-driven aspect of recent research. The in-depth examination of ensemble approaches by Nti et al. (2020c) adds depth, especially in the setting of predicting temporary market indexes. Ican & Celik (2017) highlight the significance of artificial neural networks. Considering input qualities, prediction timeframes, and accuracy while making direct stock market forecasts. The review by Kumar et al. (2021a) highlights the widespread use of neural network models, with hybrid models improving predictive power. In the Area of deep learning, Thakkar and Chaudhari (2021) offer insights into several DNN structures for stock price and pattern prediction, whereas Sezer et al.'s (2020) exploration promotes LSTM as a preferred option for its transparency and performance with time series data.

Manan Shah et al.[17] claims that ELSTM models, particularly those with built-in embeddings, have significant predictive abilities and can estimate Shanghai A-Shares with

up to 57.2% accuracy. Additionally, LSTM outperforms classic LSTM, Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), and LSTM Neural Network in denoising data on stock prices when paired with Wavelet Transform. LSTM's remarkable annualised return of 82.29% is demonstrated by Fischer & Krauss (2017) in comparison to other approaches. For S&P 500 stock analysis, Zou and Qu (2020) integrate LSTM with attention processes, producing increased predicted accuracy. Together, these studies demonstrate how effective LSTM is in improving stock market forecast accuracy.

Nusrat Rouf et al.[18] reviews Studying Stock Market Prediction (SMP) from 2011 to 2021 with a goal on how deep learning and other machine learning techniques have altered SMP. It highlights the risks that SMP faces, including those related to views shared on the internet and online dangers, and gives scholars the chance to advance security and decision making frameworks. The analysis identifies Support Vector Machines (SVM), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and Deep Neural Networks (DNN) as important SMP techniques due to their precision and efficacy. Additionally, combining market data with online text data improves the precision of forecasts. The main drawbacks and open issues with SMP systems are explained.

Vikas Choudhary et al.[19] explains the recent use of intelligent techniques by researchers in stock market prediction. By linking stock market values with RSS news feeds using sentiment analysis algorithms such as POS taggers, SSS algorithms, and lexical techniques, Bharathi et al. were able to boost forecast accuracy by 14.43%. By examining methods like SVM, LSTM, KNN, and linear regression, Vijaya Kumar B P et al. highlighted the significance of applying machine learning to forecast stock values based on sentiment analysis of social media data.

Payal Soni et al.[20] outlines the many methods and models that have been investigated by scientists for stock market prediction. The principal component analysis (PCA)-enhanced regression-based models show higher accuracy rates. While the Random Forest (RF) and MultiLayer Perceptron (MLP) do well in classification based on binary values, Support Vector Machines (also known as S excel in non-linear classification. These methods help in the creation of the best trading strategies and have greater relevance in the financial markets. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and LSTM models, two kinds of neural networks, have been used in deep learning. In terms of predicting prices for stocks, binary characteristics have shown potential. When applied to SET100 stock data, Partial Least Square (PLS), Sequential Minimal Optimisation, and Multilayer Perceptron displayed various error rates. To comprehend the dynamics of indexes like the S&P 500, LSTM models were additionally deployed.

III. METHODOLOGIES AND APPROACHES

Two popular methods for predicting the future of the stock market are technical analysis and machine learning. Technical analysis examines past market data, looking closely at elements like price changes and trading volume to spot patterns and trends. Attempts like Teixeira and De Oliveira's automatic stock trading system, which made use of historical data to create trading rules based on these discovered patterns, are examples of how this strategy has been used practically. In contrast, deep learning in machine learning uses neural networks to find patterns in huge datasets. In Ticknor's research, a Bayesian regularised artificial neural network was used to anticipate the stock

market. This network was taught to produce predictions using historical data and maybe related variables.

A. Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average

ARIMA, or Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average, is a popular time series forecasting model used in statistics and econometrics. It's a combination of three components: Autoregression (AR), Integrated (I), and Moving Average (MA). The Autoregression component captures the relationship between an observation and a number of lagged observations (i.e., observations at prior time steps). The Integrated component involves differencing the raw observations (subtracting an observation from the previous observation) to make the time series stationary. Stationarity means that the statistical properties of a time series (like mean and variance) remain constant over time.

The Moving Average component models the dependency between an observation and a residual error from a moving average model applied to lagged observations. The ARIMA model is denoted by ARIMA(p, d, q), where 'p' is the order of the autoregressive part, 'd' is the degree of differencing, and 'q' is the order of the moving average part. The parameters 'p', 'd', and 'q' are determined by examining the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation plots of the time series data. ARIMA models are widely used for forecasting in various fields, including finance, economics, and environmental science. They can capture a wide range of temporal structures and are relatively simple to implement, making them a valuable tool in time series analysis.

The formula for an ARIMA model is typically represented as:

$$Y_t = c + \phi_1 Y_{t-1} + \phi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \phi_p Y_{t-p} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- Y_t is the value of the time series at time t.
- c is a constant term or intercept.
- $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_p$ are the parameters of the autoregressive part.
- $Y_{t-1}, Y_{t-2}, \dots, Y_{t-p}$ are the lagged values of the time series.
- $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_q$ are the parameters of the moving average part.
- $\epsilon_{t-1}, \epsilon_{t-2}, \dots, \epsilon_{t-q}$ are the residuals of the model at previous time steps.
- ϵ_t is the residual at time t.

Stock Symbol	Price	LTS M	DNN	ARIMA	Most Closely
ADANIE NT.NS	3320	3000	3560	3400	ARIMA
CIPLA.NS	1460	1400	1430	1420	DNN
ITC.NS	410	400	420	414	ARIMA
RELIANCE.NS	3000	2900	2950	2980	ARIMA
TCS.NS	4010	3980	4000	4030	DNN
TITAN.NS	3736	3500	3600	3654	DNN
WIPRO.NS	514	550	528	510	ARIMA
TECHM.NS	1250	1300	1280	1264	ARIMA
NTPC.NS	358	310	332	335	ARIMA

Table 1. Comparison of Prices of Different Stocks

Category	Merits	Demerits
Traditional Machine Learning Algorithm	Traditional ML algorithms, particularly SVM, yield relatively higher accuracy as they work well with datasets of high dimensionality.	These algorithms exhibit high sensitivity to outlier
Deep-Learning	RNNs and LSTMs are the go-to Deep Learning algorithms employed for the task. RNNs offer an advantage as they capture the context of the data while training. LSTMs perform reasonably well as they can correlate the non-linear time series data in the delay state	Requires high training time and large memory requirements.
Time-Series	Time-series forecasting techniques such as ARIMA work well for linear data and provide reliable stock price forecasts for the short term	The model may not yield dependable results for long term forecasts of stock prices.
Graph-Based	Focuses on forming relationships based on correlation and causation among the nodes which is useful for exploring previously hidden insights and aids informative decision making	Traditional ML algorithms still outperform graph involved approaches in terms of accuracy.

Table 2. Different Machine Learning Models.

IV. FINDINGS AND TRENDS

The primary finding of the research highlights the widespread involvement of Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) methodology in deep learning models for stock market forecasting, with an amazing 73.5% of the studies examined using this approach. Researchers in this field frequently choose LSTM because of how well it captures sequential dependencies in time series data.

The assessment does, however, also highlight some significant gaps in the body of knowledge. For instance, the relatively few number of studies (35.3%) that examined profitability and the sparse implementation of risk management (just two publications) point to a research gap where the importance and feasibility of these models in real-world situations are still unexplored. These results show the significance of developing accurate predictions and ensuring that they result in profitable trading.

The review invites future research to explore undiscovered areas in light of these findings. In particular, this involves the creation of hybrid models that combine qualitative and quantitative input data, maybe drawing on news evaluations and macroeconomic statistics. Researchers should also concentrate on developing adaptive and clever trading strategies that can handle the volatile character of financial markets. Finally, to guarantee the sustainability and durability of deep learning techniques for stock market forecasting, it is crucial to employ effective risk management measures. These opportunities have the potential to improve the viability and accuracy of such models, furthering the development of this fascinating and developing discipline.

Sr. No	Prediction Target	Techniques	Input Parameters
1)	Stock price	ANN	Fundamental parameters
2)	Stock price of a company	Genetic Programming	Technical parameters
3)	Stock market index	ANN + DT	Micro-economical parameters
4)	Stock price of a company	ANN(FNN , RNN)	Hybrid parameters(Technical + Micro-economical)
5)	Stock price of a company	ANN	Technical parameters + User experience
6)	Stock market Index	ANN	Micro-economic indicators
7)	Stock price of a company	ANN	Hybrid parameter (Technical + Fundamental parameters)
8)	Stock price of a company	SVM	Technical parameters + News articles
9)	Highest and lowest price of a stock	ANN	Technical parameters + EMA + BB

Table 3. Different parameters

V. CHALLENGES AND GAPS

The absence of real-world application of the presented models in the investigations is a notable flaw. While these models may show accuracy or error rates in back testing or simulated environments, the dynamic and sensitive nature of the stock market, highlighted by intraday candles and susceptibility to macroeconomic data and news, presents a unique set of difficulties. The feasibility and financial viability of these models when used in live trading are questioned by the absence of real-world testing and deployment. Without a strong system to safeguard capital and extensive testing under actual conditions, doubts may persist regarding their efficiency and ability to generate profits. The review additionally highlights the dearth of research that evaluates profitability and the application of risk management techniques. Only two publications, or just 35.3% of the studies, looked at profitability or risk management. This disparity points to the urgent need for more study in these areas. Profits are the ultimate goal in stock market forecasting, and efficient risk management is crucial to maintaining capital and making sure trading techniques are long-lasting.

The reality that these important factors have received so little attention highlights how much work has to be done in this area to build deep learning models that are not only accurate but also useful and profitable. In the field of deep learning paired with technical analysis for stock market forecasting, the evaluation highlights interesting open areas for research and development.

Algorithms	Accuracy	precision	F1 score
Sparrow search algorithm(SSA)	22%	64%	NA
Decision Tree, Random Forest	86%	73%	85%
Logistic Regression and SVM	70%	75%	NA
Neural Networks	77%	63%	NA
k-fold cross validation	83.04%	92.5%	83%
ARIMA model	93%	88%	NA
LTSM,ANN algorithms	73.5%	35.3%	NA
Recurrent neural networks	80.3%	54%	NA
Artificial Neural Network	60%	65.2%	NA
Neural Network Models, Linear Regression	40%	50%	NA
Supervised & unsupervised methods	90.38%	80.59%	NA
Ensemble Methods, GARCH Method	87.66%	82.92%	74.5%

Table 4. Metrics of various Algorithms

VI. FUTURE SCOPE

There are many clients who are needing of more accuracy in the field of stock market forecasting using deep learning and technical analysis. To improve forecasting accuracy, research will increasingly focus on hybrid models that seamlessly combine qualitative and quantitative data sources. These models seek to integrate qualitative data such as news sentiment and macroeconomic variables with historical market data

The development of intelligent and adaptable trading strategies that utilises reinforcement learning methods to produce dynamic strategies that can adjust to rapidly shifting market conditions remembers to be a key priority. This improves forecasting and trading-related decision making and risk management. Effective risk management techniques will always be essential for protecting capital. To limit possible losses and ensure the sustainability of trading strategies, researchers will investigate strategies such as position planning, stop-loss mechanisms, and portfolio diversification.

Researchers will also test how successfully deep learning models apply across other markets, including numerous stock exchanges and other financial domains like commodities and currencies. This focus will also include cross-market generalisation. The near-term prospects of stock market forecasting will be determined by the creation of clever trading methods, the development of hybrid

models, and the necessity of successful risk management techniques.

VII. CONCLUSION

The stock price heavily relies on the market conditions such as interest rates, geopolitical tensions and economic growth factors. While previously these complications have been a significant obstacle for analysts and investors, recent advancements in processing power have created an explosion of study into the promise of deep learning models. The machine learning models developed as the one that is most frequently used for stock market forecasting. However, the study also identifies several limitations within the area of study, such as the absence of real-world model applications and the urgent need for further studies on profitability and risk management. The concept of hybrid models, which combine both quantitative and qualitative resources, also offers fresh possibilities for investigation. The advancements and graphical representations in the field are promising, encompassing creating the intelligent trading strategies, risk management integration, and the assessment of model generalization across diverse markets, extending beyond stock exchanges to commodities and currencies. These opportunities offer to improve our predicting skills and deepen our knowledge about the ever-evolving field of stock market analysis.

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